

ANALYSIS AND DESIGNING OF MULTILEVEL INVERTER WITH DC LINK SWITCHES CAPABLE OF POWER FACTOR CONTROL

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Abstract

More and more, grid-connected electrical converter systems are crucial as the need for renewable energy sources continues to rise. The electrical converter must fulfil the following criteria in order to operate in a grid-connected mode. A new architecture for multi-level electrical converters, based on an H-bridge with four switches linked to the dc-link, is suggested in this work. As an alternative to pulse width modulation (PWM), which uses two carrier signals, the POD (Phase opposition disposition) approach is suggested. Also taken into account is the switch sequence for balancing the voltage of the electrical gadget. Along with that, the intended architecture necessitates a minimal number of elements in order to expand the quantity and range of voltage levels. Experiment and simulation confirm the projected electrical converter's operational concept. The simulation results showed that the proposed system had a THD level of 15%, which is higher than the present system's 3%.

Key words: H-bridge, POD, PWM

1. INTRODUCTION

There is a growing need for environmentally friendly power sources, which is making network-related inverter frameworks more fundamental than ever before [1,2]. The inverter must fulfil the following requirements for network-related development.

- The inverter's output voltage must be pure sine wave.
- The inverter's output current should ideally have minimal transient harmonic distortion (THD).

For framework-tied development, a two-level PWM inverter is often used. A high exchanging rehash or a low yield channel inductance will cause a two-level inverter to fail.

meet the basic THD, it must be sufficiently large. Staggered inverters (MLIs) are introduced for structure-related inverters to adapt to the problems associated with two-level inverters. Figure 1 shows the three main types of MLI geographies that have been proposed so far: the prejudice-free point (NPC), the flying capacitor (FC), and the fallen sort [3-5]. Assuming a constant output voltage, MLIs have the potential to have a much lower exchanging rehash and device voltage rating than a conventional two-level inverter.

Consequently, the inverter framework's gainfulness may be expanded, and the risk of IGBT swapping accidents can be significantly reduced [6-8]. An H-partner geography with four alterations associated with the dc-interface is suggested as an MLI topography in this article. You can see the suggested MLI in Fig. 2. Since the suggested PWM technique only makes use of a single transporter signal to generate PWM signals, it is also instantaneous. Likewise, a trade progression was suggested that takes into account the voltage levelling of the dc-interface. In the end, the practicality of the shocked inverter's planned geology is shown by entertaining and early tests.

Fig. 1. Topologies of multi-level inverters. (a) Neutral point clamped (NPC) type. (b) Flying capacitor (FC) type. (c) Cascade type.

Operating modes and proposed PWM strategy

The yield voltage of the proposed MLI showed up in Fig. 2 has five levels (VDC, VDC/2, 0, - VDC/2, - VDC) as shown by the trading states of the inverter. There are four action modes depending upon the snappy assessment of the reference voltage, v_{ref} and the best assessment of the carrier signal, VC(see Fig. 4). Table II shows the possible inverter yield voltage level according to the working mode.

In case of the N-level NPC type staggered inverter, N-1 three-sided carrier signals with a comparable repeat and adequacy are used so they totally have contiguous gatherings over the arrive at +VDC to - VDC. A lone sinusoidal reference is diverged from each carrier signal with choose the yield voltage for the inverter. Three qualities of the carrier signal are considered to create the PWM signal [9-11].

- 1) Phase atmosphere (PD); where all carriers are in stage.
- 2) Alternative stage obstruction quality (APOD); where each carrier is stage moved by 180 degree from its close by carrier.
- 3) Phase obstruction demeanor (POD); where the carriers more than zero voltage are 180 degree out of stage with those under zero voltage.

Fig. 3 shows the reference signal and the carrier signal game-plans for PD change, POD parity, and APOD change. Another PWM procedure subject to POD change which requires only a singular carrier signal (v_{carrier}) is proposed and the low down PWM philosophy is depicted in Fig. 4. If the reference signal is positive, by then the switch pair (TA +, TB -) are turned on, and if it is negative, by then the switch pair (TA - , TB +) are turned on. Thusly the switches making the H interface inverter turned on and killed once during the hour of the reference signal. The voltage over the switch at hindering state is VDC. The switches (TP - , TN +) are worked complementally to the switches (TP +, TN -). The age of the PWM signal

or dc-interface switches (TP +, TN -) can be explained as follows

Fig. 3. Carrier and reference signal arrangements for: (a) Phase disposition (PD). (b) Alternative phase opposition disposition (APOD). (c) Phase opposition disposition (POD).

Fig. 4. PWM strategy based on POD with single carrier signal

Voltage balancing of dc-link capacitor

Fig. 5. Switching states of the proposed inverter in one cycle. (a) state 1 : $v_o = 0$. (b) state 2 : $v_o = VDC/2$. (c) state 3 : $v_o = VDC/2$. (d) state 4 : $v_o = VDC$. (e) state 5 : $v_o = 0$. (f) State 6 : $v_o = VDC/2$. (g) state 7 : $v_o = VDC/2$. (h) state 8 : $v_o = VDC$.

LITERATURE SURVEY

Nowadays, multi-level inverters are widely used in many applications due to the Increasing the number of voltage levels brings the output voltage closer to a sinusoidal wave with less harmonic content, which in

turn improves the drive's performance significantly, as seen in [4] and [5]. Voltage levelling of capacitors is only one of several features detailed in this article about the proposed inverter.

The method described in [9] produces a range of voltages by adjusting the load current using capacitors. When it comes to multilayer inverters, the neutral point clamped inverter is among the first works [6]. However, in order to stabilise the plasma and produce many voltage levels, it was suggested in [7] to employ several isolated dc sources connected by H-bridges.

Based on an analysis of the issues with the cascading multiple rectifiers theme, the work presented in [8] suggests a way to balance the capacitors. In this case, the required voltage is maintained via the capacitors by switching the load current's direction through the capacitor using the redundant states to provide an equivalent pole voltage. The ideas presented in [9] and [7] are combined in the work presented in [10]. In this case, several output voltages are produced by use of floating capacitor H-bridges.

By cycling among duplicate states with the same voltage level, the capacitors' voltages are kept at their prescribed levels. Many effective control methods are suggested in the provided publications, and they cover many features of cascaded H-bridges. Another kind of multilevel converter that may be used for motor drive applications is modular structure converters, which are well valued in HVDC applications.

A flying capacitor inverter with a cascaded design and a neutral point clamped inverter is shown. The idea of using a flying capacitor inverter with cross-connected capacitors to increase the level count has been proposed. a notable arrangement is shown for obtaining seventeen voltage levels by use of many capacitors. However, balancing the capacitor voltages immediately isn't possible. At the fundamental frequency alone will they be balanced.

EXISTING SYSTEM DEMERITS:

In existing system a SPWM approach was presented to deal with the uneven power transferring characteristics of the conventional SPWM modulation technique. This strategy end up being fruitful because of the irradiance profile and the utilization of capacitors to smooth the voltage vacillation. The framework was driven at 2 kHz in

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light of speed compels of the control stage, which required mass channel segments.

PROPOSED SYSTEM:

In the present project, I propose a new 17-level inverter formed by cascading three-level flying capacitor inverter with floating capacitor H-bridges which uses a single dc supply and derives all the required voltage levels from it. The performance of the proposed configuration is experimentally verified both for steady state operation and during transients and the results are presented.

MATLAB

Here you can provide MATLAB orders made at the brief, Not under any condition like FORTRAN and other aggregated substance, MATLAB is a deciphered environment—you give a solicitation, and MATLAB tries to execute it going before referencing another.

SIMULATION RESULTS

Using Sim2ulink SKM75GB12T4 IGBT modules, the planned 17-level inverter is brought to life. The hybrid drivers used to drive the IGBT modules are Mitsubishi M57962L. The 12-level inverter's 12 capacitors are made possible by twelve 2.2 mF capacitor banks. An auto transformer with three phases that supplies a rectifier powers the DC bus. To implement the dc bus, a bank of 1.1 mF capacitors is used. Figure 5.1 shows the experimental setup. The controller is implemented with the help of a Xilinx SPARTAN-3XC3S200 FPGA and a Texas Instruments DSP TMS320F2812. A digital signal processor (DSP) has been integrated with the motor control algorithm and level-shifted carrier based space vector PWM generating logic (by adding common mode voltage to reference voltages [24]). An FPGA with capacitor balancing logic and a strategy for generating switching states receives data on three-phase voltage levels and pulse width modulation (PWM) signals from the digital signal processor (DSP). The FPGA has integrated the dead band generating technique. There are a total of 48 (16 × 3) IGBT gating signals routed from the FPGA to the inverter modules, and each phase has 16 devices. We use LEM LV20-P hall-effect voltage sensors to measure all of the capacitor voltages. The voltages that are detected are sent to the next step by means of hysteresis comparators, which are built using LM339, and compared to a set of reference voltages.

logic device. Pulsed at 1 kHz is the inverter. A timing logic built in an FPGA ensures a precise dead time of $2\mu\text{s}$ between the complimentary signals. We scale the dc bus to 200 V dc. In order to verify the inverter's performance, a three-phase four-pole squirrel cage induction motor that is Y-connected and operates at 415 V and 50 Hz is tested using the open loop V/f technique. To evaluate the performance of the proposed inverter arrangement at different instants, the motor is driven at various frequencies and modulation indices. A modulation index of 0.2 and a frequency of 10 Hz are used to drive the motor.

Fig.5.2. Pole, Phase, capacitor voltages along with current for 10-Hz operation

of converter. VAC1(50 V/div),VAO: Pole voltage (100 V/div), VAN: Phase

Voltage (100 V/div), VAC4: (100 V/div),VAC3: (10 V/div),VAC2: (25 V/div),

IA:2 A/div, Timescale: (20 mS/div).

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Fig. 5.3. Pole, Phase, capacitor voltages along with current for 20-Hz operation of the converter. VAC1: (50 V/div),VAO: Pole voltage(100 V/div), VAN: Phase Voltage (100 V/div), VAC4: (20 V/div),VAC3: (10 V/div),VAC2: (25 V/div), IA:2 A/div, Timescale: 10 mS/div.

In Fig.5.3, we can see the motor current, voltage at the poles and phase, and voltage across the capacitors. It is clear that the voltages on the capacitors remain constant, and the increments in the output voltage are tiny. The motor is also operated at three different frequencies: 20 Hz (0.4 modulation index), 30 Hz (0.6), and 40 Hz (0.8) (see to Figs. 5.4-5.6 for details). It is clear that the controller successfully maintained voltage balance across all capacitors while operating in steady-state at different modulation indices and frequencies. There is almost no ripple in the load current, and it approaches a sinusoidal shape. We accelerate the motor from 10 to 40 Hz without load in 2.5 s to test the capacitor balancing method. The three-phase voltage reference makes its way slowly across all of the inner hexagons before reaching the outermost one. For this acceleration action, Fig.5.5 displays the motor current, pole voltage and phase voltage. Despite the machine drawing huge currents during acceleration, the experiment shows that all capacitor voltages remain consistent and the inverter correctly produces the controller-demanded voltage with little ripple. Another thing to keep in mind is that the voltage ripple of the capacitor

is close to 5% even when the inverter is drawing a

large current from the motor during abrupt transients. The inverter reliably generates the required voltage levels in steady state and during transients, as shown by the experimental results reported earlier.

Fig. 5.4. Pole, Phase, capacitor voltages along with current during sudden acceleration. VAC1:Cap AC1 voltage (100 V/div), VAO: Pole Voltage (100 V/div), VAN: Phase Voltage(100 V/div),VAC4:Cap AC4 voltage(10 V/div), VAC3:Cap AC3 voltage (20 V/div), VAC2:Cap AC2 voltage (20 V/div),IA: Phase current (2A/div) Timescale: 500 mS/div.

CONCLUSIONS& FUTURE SCOPE OF WORK

Two pulse width modulation (PWM) techniques, one based on a single carrier and the other on a level shift, are introduced. Spectra analysis, gate signal configurations, and total harmonic distortion (THD) profiles are some of the many topics covered in relation to the modulation schemes of the CHB multilevel inverters. The modulation schemes' performances are contrasted. We evaluate the performance of SPWM and SVPWM, two PWM strategies, with that of traditional PWM methods using the MATLAB/SIMULINK tools. Cluster harmonics revolving around carrier multiples are an inevitable byproduct of traditional PWM

techniques' fixed carrier frequencies.

Two pulse width modulation (PWM) techniques, sinusoidal PWM and square wave pulse width modulation (SVPWM), use a shifting carrier frequency to continually disperse the harmonics across a wideband region, significantly reducing the peak harmonics. This project is the first of its kind to compare and contrast Space Vector PWM with traditional SPWM for a two-level inverter. The results of the simulation show that, in comparison to SPWM, SVPWM produces fundamental output that is 15% better while also having superior quality, i.e. lower THD.

FUTURE SCOPE OF WORK

To test out the novel idea of reducing the number of switches, try out the hybrid H-bridge multilevel inverter. A single DC voltage source may be used with capacitors with the help of this multilevel inverter. Any of the optimisation methods, including the •Newton Raphson Method—can be used to increase performance when non-linearity arises.

•The Method of Particle Swarm Optimisation

•Method for Ant Colony Optimisation

•Gene-Based Tool

The creation of an innovative hybrid H-bridge multilevel inverter is the central topic of this dissertation. The control technique to drive the motor with real-time variable output voltage and frequency has been implemented using an FPGA controller. The FPGA controller also receives data from a voltage sensor, which allows for the management of the capacitor voltage. The designed FPGA controller opens the door to the possibility of a future closed-loop control strategy for traction motors.

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